

EMG Exploration of Bradykinesia in Parkinson's Disease: A Case Study

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Abstract— Bradykinesia is defined as slowness of movement with a progressive decrease in speed and amplitude. It is a central symptom in the diagnosis of Parkinson's disease (PD). Electromyography (EMG) signals reach maximum muscular electrical activity more slowly in subjects with PD than in healthy patients. Therefore, extracting characteristics from EMG is also important for the characterization of bradykinesia. Thus, this case study aimed to validate a previously prepared protocol seeking to extract the features and patterns of bradykinesia using EMG sensors in patients during the ON and OFF states. Features of the patient's electromyographic signals were collected using surface sensors positioned on six muscles along the upper limb while the patient performed a multi-joint task (Box and Block Test). It was observed that the root-mean-square pattern of the signal behaved similarly in both the ON and OFF stages. Regarding the median frequency, the pattern showed an increase in value throughout the execution of the task, mainly in the more distal muscles. In the present case study, some standards were observed by applying the developed protocol. Future studies will further elucidate these behavioral factors, as well as the objective assessment of bradykinesia.

Keywords — Parkinson, bradykinesia, electromyography, movement disorder, biosignal processing

I. Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is currently described as a multisystem neurodegenerative disease [1, 2]. Its prevalence and incidence constantly increase with age, but about 25% of those with the disease are under 65 years old, and 5 to 10% are under 50 [3]. The classic motor symptoms of PD are recognized as relevant elements of the disease since the initial definition of James Parkinson in the 19th century, including bradykinesia, resting tremor, muscle rigidity, and postural and gait impairment [4]. However, the disease is also characterized by the presence of non-motor symptoms [5].

Bradykinesia is defined as slowness of movement with

a progressive decrease in speed and amplitude when performing repetitive movements [6]. It is a central symptom in diagnosing PD and atypical parkinsonism [7], and in characterizing and recognizing movement disorders [8]. The analysis of bradykinesia uses Part III of the MDS-UPDRS scale and evaluates the execution of three repetitive motor tasks of the upper limbs: finger tapping, fist open-close, and pronation/supination of the hand, and of the lower limbs: toe-tapping and heel tapping [9].

Electromyography (EMG) is the quantification of electrical signals from skeletal muscles. The function of the striated muscle can be studied by analyzing the signal captured during rest and/or during muscle contraction and recording the voltage variations produced by the membrane of the muscle fibers [10]. According to Berardelli et al. [11], the EMG signal reaches the maximum muscular electrical activity more slowly in subjects with PD than in healthy patients. Therefore, extracting characteristics from EMG is also an important aspect for the characterization of bradykinesia.

In most cases, PD initially affects the upper limbs [12]. Vanmechelen et al. [13] reviewed studies to evaluate movement disorders during upper limb tasks using wearable sensors and showed that 55% were studies of PD. Regarding bradykinesia specifically, some studies used symptom measurement to monitor PD motor fluctuations more closely [14, 15], while other studies explored the objective quantification of bradykinesia compared to the UPDRS [16, 17]. Rabelo et al. used inertial measurement units (IMUs) and EMG sensors to analyze bradykinesia during a wrist extension task.

Thus, a protocol was designed with multi-joint gross (Box and Block Test) [18] to characterize bradykinesia and EMG patterns of PD. Thus, this case study aimed to validate the protocol, seeking to extract features and patterns of bradykinesia using EMG sensors in patients during the ON and OFF states.

II. Methods

A. Participant

One PD participant was tested both during the OFF phase (after at least 12 h without levodopa medication) and the ON phase (with medication). He did not have any upper limb lesion or musculoskeletal alteration or limitation that could interfere with the execution of the proposed experimental protocol.

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee on Human Research (Number 61005322.3.0000.0129) of the Instituto de Ensino e Pesquisa Alberto Santos Dumont (Number 10147). The participant was informed of the experimental procedures and asked to voluntarily provide written consent prior to the experiment.

B. Surface Electromyography

The EMG of the upper limb proximal and distal muscles was acquired using wireless surface EMG sensors (Trigno™ Wireless Systems, Delsys Inc., USA, sampling rate 1.111Hz). These sensors (37 x 27x 13 mm) are made up of 99.9% silver. Prior to sensor placement with double-sided hypoallergenic adhesive tape, the skin surface was cleaned with 70% v/v isopropyl alcohol, exfoliated and removed excessive hair, when necessary.

Six sEMG sensors were then placed in the following muscles: anterior portions of the Deltoid, the Pectoralis Major muscle, Biceps Brachii, Triceps Brachii, Extensor Carpi Radialis Brevis, and Flexor Digitorum Superficialis. As mentioned earlier, these muscles were selected for their key roles in stabilizing and moving the shoulder, elbow, wrist, and finger joints during upper limb activities and fine hand movements [19]. Electrodes were placed in the ventral portion of each muscle and parallel to the direction of the muscle fibers (Fig. 1), according to SENIAM (Surface EMG for Non-Invasive Assessment of Muscles) recommendations.

C. Tasks and procedures

The participant performed a multi-joint tasks that acquired the grosser movements of the upper limb (Box and Block Test [BBT]). While sitting down, with feet flat on the floor, hips, and knees at 90°, the subjects were instructed to place both arms on the table and remain in that position until they reached maximum relaxation, which was visually monitored using an EMG signal. Then, two audio stimuli were presented: a high-frequency stimulus (2000 Hz), indicating that the patient should start the task, and a low-frequency stimulus (1000 Hz), indicating that he should stop the movement of the task and return to the initial position of resting (one block), until hearing the initial stimulus again. While performing the tasks, participants made five scheduled stops.

After the sound stimulus, the participant was instructed to start the task as quickly as possible and use the dominant hand. The BBT was performed, which consisted of

transferring 2.5 cm wooden cubes from one side of the box to the other.

Fig. 1. Illustration of a participant seated facing the boxes with electrodes on the upper limb muscles during the Box and Block Test.

D. Data analysis

The sEMG data from the six sensors were recorded during BTT execution. All collected signals were rectified and band-pass filtered using a fourth-order Butterworth filter with a frequency range of 10–250 Hz for sEMG signals and 0.5-2 Hz for accelerometer signals. Epochs were determined based on the accelerometer data. The root mean square (RMS) and median frequency (MDF) of the epochs within each block were calculated.

III. Results

A. Clinical data

Some participant characteristics were collected before the protocol and are shown in the Table 1. A trained physiotherapist evaluated the UPDRS motor part and Hoehn and Yahr staging in the ON and OFF stages.

TABLE 1. Participant characteristics. UL = Upper Limb

	Participant
Gender	Male
Age	74
Disease duration	19 years
Medication	Prolopa, 25mg; Mantidan, 100mg
Hoehn and Yahr stage - OFF	2.5
Hoehn and Yahr stage - ON	2.5
MDS-UPDRS III - OFF	34
MDS-UPDRS III - ON	29
Bradykinesia (Right UL) - OFF	1
Bradykinesia (Right UL) - ON	2

TABLE 2. Average of feature values over the five blocks in the ON and OFF stage in Box and Block Test task.

Muscles	Feature	BBT-OFF					BBT-ON				
		B1	B2	B3	B4	B5	B1	B2	B3	B4	B5
Pectoralis Major	RMS (mV)	0,30 (0,07)	0,40 (0,04)	3,01 (0,58)	2,92 (0,85)	2,60 (0,64)	0,38 (0,48)	0,43 (0,06)	1,23 (1,02)	2,81 (0,71)	2,88 (0,45)
	MDF (Hz)	26,68 (4,81)	27,93 (6,91)	53,84 (8,77)	54,76 (8,52)	54,83 (10,35)	29,78 (5,37)	30,15 (4,73)	40,35 (14,96)	55,44 (6,47)	54,45 (7,88)
Anterior Deltoid	RMS (mV)	0,31 (0,02)	0,32 (0,03)	2,72 (0,54)	2,82 (0,81)	2,78 (0,70)	0,55 (0,85)	0,43 (0,05)	1,20 (0,99)	2,70 (0,72)	2,95 (0,67)
	MDF (Hz)	27,49 (5,16)	26,43 (5,29)	55,36 (9,11)	53,74 (8,32)	53,73 (10,64)	29,60 (5,41)	31,75 (5,54)	40,56 (15,30)	55,53 (7,20)	56,48 (8,16)
Biceps Brachii	RMS (mV)	0,96 (0,60)	0,91 (0,34)	2,57 (0,19)	2,49 (0,20)	2,57 (0,23)	0,95 (0,55)	0,90 (0,09)	1,67 (0,88)	2,72 (0,31)	3,01 (0,37)
	MDF (Hz)	31,72 (6,50)	33,81 (16,98)	89,22 (12,17)	94,71 (17,01)	95,96 (16,91)	28,93 (6,14)	26,50 (4,92)	58,47 (38,30)	91,16 (13,95)	93,65 (16,64)
Triceps Brachii	RMS (mV)	0,99 (0,6)	0,85 (0,05)	2,56 (0,31)	2,51 (0,19)	2,56 (0,23)	0,94 (0,58)	0,88 (0,09)	1,64 (0,92)	2,72 (0,36)	2,95 (0,40)
	MDF (Hz)	31,21 (7,75)	29,38 (3,20)	93,28 (14,23)	93,91 (14,95)	96,92 (16,27)	29,11 (6,93)	27,18 (4,70)	54,96 (35,19)	93,15 (12,82)	94,45 (19,03)
Flexor Digitorum Superficialis	RMS (mV)	1,75 (0,43)	1,64 (0,21)	1,14 (0,26)	1,13 (0,18)	1,01 (0,17)	1,84 (0,57)	2,14 (0,53)	1,47 (0,50)	1,23 (0,36)	1,26 (0,23)
	MDF (Hz)	98,38 (18,68)	101,61 (17,92)	115,64 (29,41)	125,75 (27,55)	122,94 (24,76)	83,13 (16,40)	92,41 (19,30)	101,65 (22,02)	127,83 (30,62)	127,49 (22,67)
Extensor Carpi Radialis Brevis	RMS (mV)	1,69 (0,36)	1,58 (0,29)	1,05 (0,15)	1,10 (0,15)	1,02 (0,16)	1,79 (0,40)	1,93 (0,42)	0,91 (0,42)	1,19 (0,24)	1,26 (0,24)
	MDF (Hz)	103,13 (18,55)	106,33 (22,89)	123,77 (30,68)	122,07 (32,37)	122,46 (24,96)	89,40 (17,10)	93,99 (17,02)	44,10 (17,02)	123,84 (22,04)	131,59 (26,81)

BBT=Box and Block Testet; B1=Block 1; B2=Block 2; B3=Block 3; B4=Block 4; B5=Block5. RMS= Root Mean Square; MDF= Median Frequency.

B. EMG characteristics in ON and OFF stages

The averaged values of the features calculated are listed in Table 2. In it we can observe the RMS and MDF values of the six muscles studied in the present work. The values are shown along the five blocks that occur in the execution of the task, for the ON and OFF stages.

IV. Discussion

The motor unit recruitment reflected by the RMS values increased along the blocks, with a notable change in the proximal muscles from the third block. However, an inverse relationship was observed in wrist muscles. The flexor and extensor muscles were more activated in the first and second blocks and gradually reduced until the last block. These findings are expected, considering that BBT is an outcome measure that requires a flexion and horizontal adduction of the shoulder to move the cubes from one side to the other, which promotes more amplitude movements of the shoulder and elbow joints. Meanwhile, it requires smaller movements of the hand and isometric muscle activation to hold the cube.

Comparing this pattern of activation between the ON and OFF stages, a more gradual increase in activation from the third block was observed in the ON stage. This could be explained by the good responsiveness of bradykinesia and rigidity to the levodopa action on the nigrostriatal pathway, which improves voluntary motor control [20]. During the ON stage, the subject also presented dyskinesias that led to more extensive and faster movements associated with involuntary trunk and lower limb movements on the more affected side. However, it did not affect the performance during the test.

One of the features of bradykinesia is the impairment of speed or amplitude during sequential movements and the

sequence effect [21]. An experimental study with thirteen PD participants found that the sequence effect is associated with higher movement energy cost to maintain the performance on a fine motor task [22], and also showed that dopaminergic treatment did not improve this effect. This phenomenon could explain the gradual lower activation of the wrist flexor and extensor muscles observed during the BBT in both ON and OFF stages, due to the sequential and repetitive movement of opening and closing the hand to catch the cubes.

Another piece of data observed in our results was the number of back and forth movements performed by the participant throughout each block. This value also remained similar in the ON and OFF stages, but the range of motion when passing the hand over the barrier between one side of the box and the other was greater during the ON stage, as observed in the task, particularly in the last blocks. This was due to the action of levodopa [23]. However, inertial analysis along with electromyography is essential to make this pattern even clearer and to seek objective measurements. Inertial sensors are increasingly being used in PD analyses [13].

V. Conclusion

In the present case study, we concluded that the subjects' RMS maintained a similar pattern in the ON and OFF stages throughout the trials. The MDF showed a similar pattern for all muscles, especially the more distal ones, with an increase in the last trials. With the present protocol, we can extract the characteristics of bradykinesia, which can help in the accuracy of the diagnosis of PD and the evaluation of its evolution, and can also help in future studies that aim to compare the patterns of bradykinesia in PD with those present in other motor disorders.

Acknowledgment

The present work was carried out with the support of the Ministry of Education (MEC), National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq), Coordination for the Improvement of Higher Education Personnel (CAPES) (CAPES - Program CAPES/DFATD - 8887.159028/2017-00, Program CAPES/COFECUB - 88881.370894/2019-01, Program CAPES - 88887.849144/2023-00) and the Foundation for Research Support of the State of Minas Gerais (FAPEMIG). A. O. Andrade is fellow of CNPq, Brazil (302942/2022-0).

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